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Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
JRAs	Joint Research Activities
LLL	Living Lab Lexicon
IRL	Innovation Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
CRL	Customer Readiness Level
LLBM	Living Lab Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
B2B	Business-to-Business
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
PCP	Pre-commercial Procurement

Executive summary

Although Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have been shown to be a “key” to the integration of research and innovation processes in real-life settings, they still fail to provide and function according to unified and harmonized processes that are easily accessible and exploitable by academic and industry researchers. Towards this end, VITALISE aims to create the first Harmonization guidelines for Living Labs that will facilitate the access of researchers to the provided infrastructures.

This document presents the work performed for the Harmonization of the way Living Labs work for the fourth semester of VITALISE. Within the VITALISE project, various Harmonization activities were carried out with consortium partners and external stakeholders, to develop the Standard v0.4, building on the work done for the earlier versions of the Standard (v0.1, v0.2 and v0.3). The first version of the Standard (v0.1) provided an overview of the state-of-the-art information about Living Labs in the VITALISE consortium and served as the foundational deliverable for the VITALISE Standards. The second version of the Standard (v0.2) introduced the process of developing and disseminating a Wiki page that incorporated v0.1 and updated the parts of the Standard that described the data and technologies used in living labs, using a Delphi study method, and collected the initial set of terms for the living lab lexicon. Additionally, during the second semester, the Harmonization Board was established, and a meeting with the Harmonization Body was held. In the third version of the Standard (v0.3) the device and technology taxonomy were updated through a Delphi study, several meetings were held for updating the services and procedures categorization, as well as several activities and sessions for collecting and achieving a preliminary agreement on living lab lexicon terms. Moreover, two templates were developed for the co-creation sessions conducted within the Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and also, during this third semester, the project held its second plenary meeting in Helsinki and the second Harmonization Body meeting.

During this iteration for the current deliverable (Standard Version 0.4), a wide range of actions took place, starting with meetings and activities to update the LL Lexicon terms. Moreover, several activities were carried out toward the definition of the LL Innovation and Research phases, as well as to update the LL services. In addition, an analysis of the Open Call data was conducted regarding the stakeholders, the services, and devices provided by the LLs, and also some interviews with consortium partners and external experts regarding several aspects of the research processes. The analysis of the results of those interviews is planned to be presented in the next Standard Version, since more interviews are planned to be performed within the upcoming period. Furthermore, we proceeded with the finalization of data and devices taxonomy from the Delphi study and their approval from the Harmonization Board. Last but not least, during this semester, the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting and one Harmonization Board meeting took place on January and February correspondingly.

The final Section of this document presents the Standard v0.4 that will be also published in the living lab harmonization wiki page.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2), “Common Standards, Procedures and Practices” is a core WP for the VITALISE project as it handles all the work and implementation for the Harmonization procedure that is being followed. Some of the main tasks are the establishment of the harmonization procedures within the consortium and beyond, the management and organization of the Harmonization procedure events (Harmonization Body and Board meetings) and the definition and update of the Standards and Key Performance Indicators by identifying and documenting the existing Living Lab processes, and the similarities and differences among the consortium’s Living Lab partners. The Standard Versions will be updated every six months until the end of VITALISE project.

VITALISE Harmonization Body is a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to coordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and consists of representatives from each Living Lab in the consortium, independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document aims to present all the data collection and analysis that has been done between M18-M24 of the VITALISE project regarding the Harmonization activities. Although the deliverable is entitled “Standard Version 4”, the authors of this document decided that the specific standard should be Version 0.4 as it does not yet include all the parts required to reach Version 1.0. This will be the final version of the Standard and it is going to be released by the end of the project on M36. This document does not include only the Standard Version 0.4 of the Living Labs services, methods and tools but a more elaborate version, that includes the presentation of data collection, activities and analysis in order to result in the next Standard Version.

1.3 Document Structure

The deliverable is structured as such:

- **Section 1** (this section) provides information regarding the VITALISE project, aspects related to it, and the purpose of the document.
- **Section 2** discusses the activities that were performed during the third semester of living lab harmonization framework towards the creation of Standard v0.4.
- **Section 3** presents a summary of the changes and new additions that were made to the current version of the standard.
- **Section 4** includes all the information that will constitute the Standard Version 0.4. This Section is a coherent version of the Standard and can be read as a standalone document.
- **Section 5** provides some concluding remarks on this deliverable.

2 Activities performed towards the next standard version

During the fourth iteration for the improvement of Living Lab Standard, the Harmonization objectives were to proceed with the Living Lab Lexicon task, but also with the activities towards the definition of the Living Lab Innovation Phases and the Research phases. Moreover, in the current Standard version were executed several activities aiming to update the Living Lab services, analyze the results of the Open Call data about the stakeholders, the services and devices provided by the LLs and finalize the taxonomy of data and devices. Lastly, one Harmonization Body meeting and one Harmonization Board meeting were held during this iteration. This section presents the activities carried out to achieve these objectives.

2.1 Living Lab Lexicon Creation

The main objective of the Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) was to identify and define words/terms often used in a Living Lab setting to facilitate and increase the common understanding and communication between the different 'players' within the Living Lab communities and all those who encounter Living Labs. The following goals were determined as a group: 1) determine which words/terms to define, 2) consider who the target audience(s) is (are), and 3) identify existing definitions (when available). However, before this could begin, they first needed to establish a process that would result in the definitions of the selected terms within the context of LLs. This process was established by consensus over the course of two meetings.

Wanting to go beyond their personal experience with Living Labs the group settled on a more objective process and compiled a corpus comprised of articles using Living Lab methodology and the ENoLL Open Living Lab Days Proceedings from 2013-2022. To identify and select the articles to include in the corpus, they created a search strategy that included terms commonly used by those who use a Living Lab methodology and conducted a multifile search of three databases, (MEDLINE, EMBASE, and PsycInfo) in August 12, 2022. This resulted in 567 articles identified and, of these, 173 articles included in the corpus. The selection was done by two independent reviewers based on review of the title and abstract of each article. The corpus of articles identified through the search AND the ENoLL Proceedings were entered in the word mining software, WordStat which allowed the group to calculate frequency counts and % of cases (i.e. the % of articles that a word/term was present) for all of the terms in the corpus. Once the words/terms were sorted in terms of frequency of occurrence, number of cases, % of cases and length (1, 2, 3 words) the groups proceeded to select which first set of words/terms should first be defined and included in the Living Lab Lexicon. Selection of this first set of words/terms was done based on the frequency counts (i.e., those terms that appeared with a high frequency in the corpus) as well as based on the group's opinion (i.e., 4 group members voted on which of the high frequency words/terms to include first).

In parallel, some of these terms were chosen to be given as an assignment in the MSc in Medical Engineering and Informatics (MEI) of AUTH. Two sets of words were given to two student groups. For each word, they have been asked to identify the following:

1. A set of 3-4 different definitions. The definitions can be found in scientific or grey literature.
2. Identify the source of definition and write a short explanation of why you have chosen to include that definition. Pay attention to the scientific credibility of the source and include information like credibility of the journal, number of citations/mentions of the source and/or definition, and credibility of the author. Also specify the context of the definition.
3. Provide a combined definition based on the ones that were identified previously (Step 1)

Each team was asked to submit one file in which they included the identified sources and definitions, one explanation for each source and the combined definitions. The two sets of words were:

GROUP 1 term

- Living lab/Living Labs
- End user/end users
- Innovation process

- Case studies/case study
- Participatory design
- User driven

GROUP 2 terms

- Open Innovation
- Innovation management
- Multi stakeholder
- User centered
- Focus group
- Design thinking

Since words/terms are harder to understand when seen in isolation, the group then proceeded to create a concept map built around existing definitions from ENOLL with additional words/terms added from the new list. The end of this stage coincided with the VITALISE 2023 plenary meeting in Vienna, so the group seized this opportunity to conduct a group consultation activity to validate the process that has been followed up until that point and to gather feedback regarding the first set of definitions with the consortium members present. While validation of the concept map was achieved with minor changes being required, it is understood that this map will likely change with time as additional terms are added. In collaboration with the consortium members, definitions for a first subset of terms were tweaked when needed resulting in list of terms that were accepted by all. These terms include “Living Lab”, “Co-creation”, “Lead user”, “End-user”, “Customer”, “Expert”, and “Non-user”.

The next steps involve continuing to identify and define words/terms from the list and adding them to the concept map with the ultimate goal of publishing the concepts map and definitions that will comprise the Living Lab Lexicon on the VITALISE website.

2.2 Activities towards updating the Living Lab services

In the current iteration, one of the key objectives was to update the Living Lab services and the work that has been done so far. Based on comments from the Open Calls applicants, we identified a misunderstanding among the several provided services. To clarify this issue, we started by trying to map each service as back-office, supporting and Research & Development services (R&D). For this reason, it was considered crucial to provide a concrete definition for each one of these categories, so that everyone has a common understanding of them. The following definition were given:

Back-office services: the services that refer to processes which take place behind-the-scenes and do not involve customers or clients. In this category is included a wide range of jobs and tasks depending on the organization’s/company's structure. In this way, back-office services provide important functions that contribute to the success of the organization.

Supporting services refers to those services which provide the necessary support, as auxiliary processes, to ensure that a research study will run in an efficient and safe manner.

Research & Development services: refer to the process by which an organization/company works to generate new knowledge that might be used to innovate and introduce new technology, products, services, or systems - or to improve their existing offerings - which, afterwards, will be either used or sold.

After mapping the services in one of the aforementioned categories, we tried to define which input is needed for each one of them and from whom this input is provided (from the Living Labs or the clients). The expected output from each service was described as well. It is important to note that from this process, we came up with some additional services, which are not reported in the current Standard Version as not all the information has been clarified. All this work and the activities implemented towards the update of the LL services were presented to the consortium partners during the Harmonization Body Meeting on 17/1/2023 (see section 2.6) and in the Harmonization Board meeting on 10/2/2023.

2.3 Harmonization Board and Body meetings

The Harmonization Board and Body meetings are the core activities in each Standard version development as they bring together the community of Living Labs (Body) and the community of experts (Board) so that they discuss and take important decisions for the progress of the VITALISE standards.

On the 17th of January 2023, the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting was held, with main objective to discuss the next steps of the Harmonization process. A few days prior to the meeting, an online questionnaire was created and shared with the participants through the “SurveyMonkey” platform, aiming to map the Living Lab services with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) and Customer Readiness Level (CRL) phases. The questionnaire process and results are described in Section 2.3 below.

In the beginning of the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting, after a short introduction by the Project Coordinator, the existing updates about the Harmonization Process and the current Standard Version were presented. Afterwards, as mentioned above, the work that has been implemented during this semester regarding the services categorization, was presented to the Harmonization Body members, in order for them to express their opinions, share any comment or objection they may have and, eventually reach a consensus upon the proposed categorization about back-office, supporting and R&D services. The definitions of the three aforementioned categories were also presented to assure that all the meeting participants perceive those categories in the same way. Then the results of the TRL/CRL questionnaire in “SurveyMonkey” platform were presented and discussed, aiming to give a total distribution comparison among TRL and CRL, as well as a TRL and a CRL distribution by each service, highlighting the main results that were occurred.

The last part of the Harmonization Body meeting was a workshop using “menti.com” platform, asking the participants to suggest some LL value propositions for specific target groups (researchers, policy makers & public authorities, SMEs/companies) and, also, for the Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 1-3, TRL 4-6, TRL 7-9). In sum, the 3rd Harmonization Body meeting resulted in fruitful discussions and action points regarding the next Harmonization steps, giving the opportunity to the participants to share their feedback and opinions about the current status and also the upcoming updates in the next Standard version.

Figure 1 Snapshot from the Harmonization Body meeting

On the 10th of February 2023, a Harmonization Board meeting took place. The main objectives of this meeting were initially the approval of the Taxonomy for Data & Devices and, also, the presentation of the Harmonization Body results about the services categorization. The key-point that was highlighted by almost all the participants was that apart from the typical services, there are also extended services that are more linked to the LL way of thinking and operating and that we should focus more on the LL values and the characteristics that are unique and specific for the LLs. Moreover, another focus of the discussion was on the next steps of the Harmonization process, as well as on a proposed common publication that will present the VITALISE Harmonization methodology.

Following to the meeting, the information about the updates on the services that were presented was sent to all the Harmonization Board members, kindly requesting them any suggestion for improvement they may have. In addition, a short questionnaire was also distributed to them, in order to gather and analyse their views and insights on what are the LL value propositions for researchers, policy makers and public authorities as well as SMEs and companies.

Figure 2 Snapshot from the Harmonization Board meeting

The analysis of the Harmonization Body results led to the definition of Living Lab Innovation Phases (Section 2.3 below) and the approval of the distinction of services in Back office, Supporting and Research and Development. More data were collected regarding the value proposition of Living Labs, both from the Harmonization Body and Board, but the results are not yet gone through the validation phase.

Throughout this iteration, we finalized the Delphi study for creating a taxonomy of data and devices for Living Labs. The results were communicated to the Harmonization Board in order to provide further comments or changes. During the Harmonization Board meeting the Board members unanimously approved the current version of taxonomy. This version is considered as stable and we do not expect major changes until the end of the project. The Harmonization Board also approved the distinction of services in Back office, Supporting and Research and Development.

2.4 Activities towards definition of the Living Lab Research and Innovation Phases

An online survey was conducted to evaluate what kind of services living labs are offering in different technology readiness level stages. KTH Innovation Readiness Level™ (IRL) framework¹ was selected as theoretical framework for the evaluation. Besides technology readiness, IRL includes also five other dimensions including customer, business, IPR, team and funding. However, only technology readiness and customer readiness scales were adopted for the survey. The following questions were asked from VITALISE living labs:

- If your living lab is testing/co-creating a solution in a specific Technology Readiness Level (TRL), which of the services will you use?
- If your living lab is testing/co-creating a solution in a specific Customer Readiness Level (CRL), which of the services will you use?

Respondents were asked to select as many services for each TRL- and CRL-level as they wish. The definitions for each TRL and CRL steps were provided for respondents. Furthermore, a list of services (N=27) currently presented in the standard were included as options.

¹ <https://kthinnovationreadinesslevel.com/>

The number of living labs responding to the survey was six. Table 1 presents the survey results for CRLs and Table 2 for TRLs.

Table 1 Survey results for CRLs

Number of respondents = 6	Number of LL having a service	CRL 1	CRL 2	CRL 3	CRL 4	CRL 5	CRL 6	CRL 7	CRL 8	CRL 9
Total		19%	19%	25%	28%	38%	35%	39%	15%	7%
1. Access to data	4	33%	33%	17%			17%			
2. Intake and matching	6	67%	50%	50%	50%	67%	50%	50%	50%	33%
3. Capacity building	6			50%	33%	67%	33%	17%		17%
4. Clinical trials	3	17%	17%		17%	17%				
5. Co-creation session	6	50%	50%	50%	50%	83%	33%	50%	33%	17%
6. Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	6	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	67%	33%	17%	17%
7. Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study	6			50%	67%	50%	33%	17%		
8. Equipment and facility rental service	4					17%	33%	17%		
9. Expert opinion, and advisory services	5	33%	33%	33%	33%	50%	33%	67%	33%	17%
10. Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	4	33%	17%	17%	50%					
11. Temporary research funding	5	17%	33%	50%	33%	50%	33%	50%		
12. Grant writing and funding application support service	4		17%			17%	17%	50%		
13. Idea selection and testing	6	33%	50%	67%	33%	17%	33%	33%	17%	
14. Impact assessment and validation test	6			17%	33%	50%	67%	33%	17%	
15. Innovation network orchestration	5	17%	17%	33%	33%	33%	33%	83%	17%	17%
16. Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	5				17%			50%	50%	17%
17. Legal, regulation and safety standard support	4		17%	17%	17%	17%	17%	33%		
18. Living Lab project planning and management	5	17%	33%	50%	50%	67%	50%	50%	33%	17%
19. Marketing and sales support	4	17%			17%	33%	17%	17%	33%	17%
20. Panel management	6	33%	33%	67%	50%	50%	50%	83%	17%	
21. Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	5	17%				17%		17%	50%	17%
22. Prototyping test	6				17%	50%	83%	33%		
23. Public procurement support services	4	17%			17%	17%	17%	17%	17%	
24. Simulation test	5				17%	33%	33%	50%		
25. Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation	6				17%	50%	83%	50%		
26. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping	6	50%	50%	50%	50%	50%	67%	67%	33%	
27. Usability testing	6				17%	67%	50%	83%		

Table 2 Survey results for TRLs

Number of respondents = 6	Number of LL having a service	TRL 1	TRL 2	TRL 3	TRL 4	TRL 5	TRL 6	TRL 7	TRL 8	TRL 9
Total		25%	24%	28%	41%	38%	39%	33%	30%	21%
1. Access to data	6	50%	50%	33%	67%	67%	67%	50%	33%	33%
2. Intake and matching	6	50%	50%	50%	67%	67%	50%	50%	67%	50%
3. Capacity building	6	33%	33%	33%	67%	50%	50%	33%	33%	67%
4. Clinical trials	3	17%			33%	17%				
5. Co-creation session	6	50%	50%	50%	67%	67%	33%	33%	33%	17%
6. Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking	6	50%	50%	50%	50%	33%	50%	50%	33%	33%
7. Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study	6	17%	33%	50%	50%	50%	17%	17%	17%	17%
8. Equipment and facility rental service	4				33%	17%	17%	50%	17%	
9. Expert opinion, and advisory services	6	50%	50%	50%	83%	67%	50%	50%	67%	33%
10. Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	4	33%	17%		17%		17%			17%
11. Temporary research funding	6	33%	33%	33%	67%	67%	50%	50%	17%	
12. Grant writing and funding application support service	4			33%					17%	50%
13. Idea selection and testing	6	50%	50%	50%	17%	17%	17%	17%		33%
14. Impact assessment and validation test	6				50%	33%	67%	67%	33%	
15. Innovation network orchestration	5	33%	33%	33%	33%	50%	33%	50%	50%	17%
16. Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	6				17%		33%	50%	83%	
17. Legal, regulation and safety standard support	4		17%		17%		17%	17%		
18. Living Lab project planning and management	6	50%	50%	50%	50%	83%	50%	50%	50%	33%
19. Marketing and sales support		17%			17%		17%	17%	17%	
20. Panel management		50%	50%	67%	50%	50%	83%	50%	33%	33%
21. Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing		17%	17%						17%	17%
22. Prototyping test				33%	67%	50%	67%	50%	17%	
23. Public procurement support services		17%	17%	17%	17%	17%	33%	33%	17%	17%
24. Simulation test				50%	33%	33%	50%		17%	
25. Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation				17%	33%	50%	67%	17%	17%	17%
26. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping		50%	50%	50%	50%	83%	50%	50%	67%	33%
27. Usability testing					50%	50%	67%	50%	50%	50%

As a result, it appeared that many of the services were crosscutting all the TRL and CRL phases. Therefore, only in a few cases we can make a clear conclusion, what kind of services living labs are offering in a specific phase. The following service have strong presence in the given TRL and CRL level (i.e., over 80 percent of living lab argue having this service in the particular phase):

- TLR 4: Expert opinions
- TRL 5: Living lab project planning and management; Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping
- TRL 6: Panel management
- TRL 8: Large-scale real-life testing and piloting
- CRL 5: Co-creation session
- CRL 6: Prototype testing; Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation
- CRL 7: Innovation network orchestration; Panel management; Usability testing

However, it is argued that in some cases there was a bit confusion among respondents regarding the TRL and CRL definitions. For example, one living lab claimed that they are offering “Large-scale real-life testing and piloting” in TRL 4 level, which by the definition takes place in laboratory. Therefore, it appears that there was still a need to clarify and refine TRL-level and service definitions in a way that they are easier to interpret. As a result, development work “TRL-levels for living lab research” was started. Literature review was done to compare different TRL definitions and how the different frameworks define the steps. Furthermore, definitions for the terms presented in these descriptions were also collected in order to understand more precisely the difference between the levels. For example, it is not very clear when a prototype is at low or moderate level. Moreover, the difference between concept and prototype is also blurry. Therefore, to avoid confusion, it would be valuable if there is more precise indicators or characteristics defined for each TRL step. This development work was started by presenting literature review-based model.

2.5 Analysis of Open Call data

At the beginning of the project, a key objective was to obtain a comprehensive and inclusive understanding of VITALISE Living Labs in order to gather valuable information that would later serve the Open Call purposes. For this reason, all the engaged to VITALISE Living Labs, were kindly asked to provide some information to a shared excel file regarding the end-users and stakeholders they can have access to, their use cases/research expertise, the services they offer, as well as the devices and technologies they usually use.

Customer segments

In particular, regarding the end-users and stakeholders that the partner LLs can have access to, a classification was done based on the age group and the health status for the non-professional end-users, as well as a classification for the professional end users, students and organisations, commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research projects. In the Table below we present also the information about which LLs from the VITALISE consortium have access to each category of stakeholders (Table 3). This activity will be extended to all LLs in the community.

Table 3 Classification approaches of non-professional and professional end-users

Stakeholders	Per Health Condition	Per Living Lab
Adolescents	Healthy	Laurea Activity Lab

Adults	Healthy, Schizophrenia, Multiple-Sclerosis, Parkinson Disease, Post-Stroke Patients with Moving or Linguistic Disability, Mild Cognitive Impairment, Sleep Disorders: e.g. Apnea, Hypopnea, With Disability, Healthy/Possible Chronic Conditions	AUTH, Licalab, McGill, INTRAS, Laurea Activity Lab
Older Adults	Healthy, Parkinson Disease, Mild Cognitive Impairment, With Disability, Healthy/Possible Chronic Conditions	UTH, Licalab, UPM, McGill, INTRAS, GAIA, AIT, TREBAG, Laurea Activity Lab
General Population	Healthy, Ipf Patients, Prostate Cancer, Down Syndrome, Chronical Diseases: e.g. Persons With Chronic Pulmonary (Copd), Cardiological Or Other Conditions (Aphasia), Breast Cancer Survivors, Chronical Diseases: e.g. Persons With Chronic Pulmonary (Copd), Cardiological Or Other Conditions (Aphasia)	AUTH, UPM, AIT, Laurea Activity Lab, LAUREA Simulated Hospital
Informal Caregivers	n.a.	AUTH, Licalab, UPM, INTRAS, AIT
Health Care Professionals / Formal Caregivers	n.a.	AUTH, Licalab, UPM, INTRAS, AIT, Laurea Activity Lab, LAUREA Simulated Hospital
Students	n.a.	AUTH, LAUREA Simulated Hospital
Organizations	n.a.	Licalab, UPM, INTRAS, AIT, Laurea Activity Lab

An analysis was made also regarding the researchers' expertise to whom each LL infrastructure can provide support. The total number of VITALISE LL research infrastructures that support each researcher is specified along with the presentation of the specific LLs (Table 4).

Table 4 Researchers' expertise

Researchers' expertise	Brief use case description	total number of infrastructures	Living Labs
Accessibility design experts	Validating accessible architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations.	8	AIT, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea

Applied economics experts	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health.	3	AUTH, GAIA
Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state).	9	AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, UPM, Laurea
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market.	9	LiCalab, AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS, Laurea
Citizen scientists, users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation.	13	AIT, LiCalab, AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, UPM, Laurea
Clinical expertise researchers	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g., via real life testing.	10	MOBILAB, Thomas More, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea
Communication studies experts	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab).	6	AIT, AUTH, TREBAG, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea

Computer, technology scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity.	13	AIT, LiCalab, MOBILAB, Thomas More, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, UPM, Laurea
Data scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations).	11	AIT, LiCalab, MOBILAB, Thomas More, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR
Ergonomics and safety experts	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards.	8	AIT, AUTH, INTRAS, Laurea
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization.	9	AIT, TREBAG, GAIA, INTRAS, Laurea
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behavior and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation).	7	AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR
Organizational studies experts	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / pier support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes.	8	AIT, AUTH, INTRAS, Laurea

Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab).	4	AUTH, TREBAG, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea
Performing arts experts	Creative health improvement (e.g., for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance).	5	TREBAG, GAIA, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea
Policymakers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making.	10	AUTH, GAIA, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, UPM, Laurea
Psychologists (clinical, social, developmental, neuro)	Studying the behavior and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing.	7	AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR
Rehabilitation (physical, cognitive) experts	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology.	11	LiCalab, MOBILAB, Thomas More, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea
Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society.	7	AUTH, TREBAG, INTRAS, Laurea
Sport science	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features.	7	AUTH, TREBAG, GAIA, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, Laurea

<p>UX research and assessment experts</p>	<p>Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behaviour through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user’s experience in different situations and while using different tools.</p>	<p>11</p>	<p>AIT, LiCalab, AUTH, INTRAS, McGill-UdeM-CRIR, UPM, Laurea</p>
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R&D Services

LL infrastructures were asked to fill in which R&D services they offer. The services were listed and presented based on the frequency with which the infrastructures offer them.

3 Updates on the Standard

This Section summarizes the updates that were made in the corresponding Standard Version 0.4 compared to the previous one, Standard Version 0.3. Some Parts are updated (Part 1, Part 2.2 and Part 5) and some are completely new, included in this Standard for the first time (Part 3, Part 4). As we are moving towards the final version of the Standard for the VITALISE project, our goal is to include information in each Section.

3.1 Part 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

The Living Lab Lexicon comprised of the words/terms and definitions as well as the concept map that shows the relationships between these words/terms. This is the first validated version of the concept map and updates will be applied in the next version.

3.2 Part 2.2 Customer segments

The updates introduced on this part, are coming from the results produced by the analysis of the Open Call data, presented in Section 2.5. The updates refer to the Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs and the Researcher expertise. A different representation was decided for the Standard version, excluding the information for the specific VITALISE LLs from Table 1 and 2. The customer segments were divided in non-professionals and professionals. The categorization of non-professionals was done primarily based on age and then we specified the health conditions of the population. The professionals were divided in 4 categories, healthcare professionals, informal caregivers, students and organizations. The table (Table 9) presenting the Researchers' expertise was sorted based on the frequency identified in Table 2.

3.3 Part 3. Research process

Table 5 presents common research process steps and how different living lab services and key assets are linked to each step.

Table 5 Living Lab Research process phases

Phases	Research process steps	Related living lab services
Planning phase	1. Identifying the research problem	1. Use living lab capacity building services to gain knowledge and skills to conduct your own living lab study.
	2. Conduct literature review and collect other relevant background information	2. Conduct small pre-study with a living lab. Use e.g., co-creation sessions or expert opinion services to gain better understanding of the research topic or to formulate robust research design.
	3. Formulate research questions and/or hypothesis	3. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping with living lab to determine suitable sample.
	4. Define the research design and determine sample	4. Use open data repository and omit data collection entirely or partially.
Preparation phase	Acquire funding	1. Apply temporary living lab research funding if it is available e.g., via open call. 2. Utilize living lab grant writing and funding application support services or join to consortium who is applying funding. 3. Use living lab networking services to gain access with funders.

	Research infrastructure selection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Get in contact with a living lab and familiarize yourself with their research infrastructure key assets and service offerings. Living lab research infrastructure covers single-sited, distributed, virtual access and mobility facilities, which each have different strengths. 2. Clarify your research needs in intake and matching process with potential living lab infrastructure providers. Wait for their offer. 3. Send equipment and/or facility rental request to a living lab.
	Ethic approval	Living lab will prepare and manage ethical application process for your study.
	Participant recruitment	Living lab will use their stakeholder population repository to recruit study participants for the study.
Implementation phase	5. Data collection	Living lab will conduct data collection according to research protocol and will manage the project for you. You will benefit from wide range available methods, tools, devices, technologies, validated questionnaires and instruments, which can be tailored to your research needs.
	6. Analyze data	Living lab will conduct data analysis if agreed in project contract. Translations or summary reports from local language to English are made if there isn't common language between customer and collected data.
	7. Interpret results	Discuss and interpret result in a co-creative manner with diverse group of experts from living lab innovation ecosystem.
	8. Write research report	Co-author scientific and professional publications with living lab researchers.
Dissemination and valorisation	9. Disseminate findings	Utilize living lab sales, marketing and networking services to disseminate and valorise your research results to various stakeholder groups. Gain visibility by sharing your publication in living lab publication repository.

3.4 Part 4. Innovation process

Innovation process is a set of structured and systematic steps to translate an idea into a new marketable solution. In literature many approaches have been presented to describe living lab innovation process phases with varying step names (Schuurman, 2016; Coorevits, 2018; Santonen, 2020; Van Den Kieboom, 2019). This causes confusion among living lab actors and their customers. For standard purposes it is vital to define innovation process steps that would be universally accepted and widely known also beyond living lab community. The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scales are commonly used and widely accepted framework for assessing the maturity of technologies and describing the current innovation process stage. Table 6 presents commonly used TRL scales (Héder, 2017).

Table 6 Technology Readiness Scale

TRL Level	European Commission	ISO 16290 systems	standard Space	KTH Innovation Readiness Level	UK House of Commons, Technology and Innovation Centres
TRL 1	Basic principles observed	Basic principles observed and reported		Interesting research results or initial technology idea identified	Basic principles observed and reported.
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated	Technology concept and/or application formulated		Technology concept and/or application formulated	Technology concept and/or application formulated.
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept		Proof-of-concept of critical functions and/or characteristics in laboratory	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof of concept.
TRL 4	Technology validated in lab	Component and/or breadboard functional verification in laboratory environment		Technology validation in laboratory	Technology basic validation in a laboratory environment.
TRL 5	Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)	Component and/or breadboard critical function verification in relevant environment		Technology validation in relevant environment	Technology basic validation in a relevant environment.
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key	Model demonstrating the critical functions of the element in a relevant environment		Technology prototype demonstration in relevant environment	Technology model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment.

	enabling technologies)			
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in operational environment	Model demonstrating the element performance for the operational environment	Technology prototype demonstration in operational environment	Technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment.
TRL 8	System complete and qualified	Actual system completed and accepted for flight ("flight qualified")	Technology complete and demonstrated in actual operations	Actual Technology completed and qualified through test and demonstration.
TRL 9	Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)	Actual system "flight proven" through successful mission operations	Technology complete and proven in actual operations	Actual Technology qualified through successful mission operations.

Technology Readiness Level Framework for the living labs is suggested to be suitable approach to define and describe living lab innovation process maturity stage. However, in living lab innovation process, the “Technology” term must be interpreted as any product/service/system/method/ solutions or similar tangible realization of the idea that is being developing, not only as “technology” per se. Therefore, term “solution” is preferred in living lab context instead of technology. Table 7 define living lab TRL levels titles and summarize each step main purpose and objectives.

Table 7 Proposed Living Lab TRL

Title	Main purpose and objectives
TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation	A need is a measurable gap between two conditions: what currently is and what should be, whereas ideation is a process of creating and prioritizing new ideas. The key objectives are to identify market demand, potential users, user needs, latent needs, (hidden) problems, competitive landscape and challenge these from different stakeholders' perspective. Often a state of the art of the current scientific literature is also covered to define what is already known in prior research.
TRL 2: Concept co-creation	Concept is high-level, abstract representation of an idea describing the overall vision and direction of the developed solution. Co-creation refers to collaboration in which various key stakeholders are actively contributing in solution development. Defines and prioritizes solution key characteristics and makes value proposition hypothesis by exploring and co-creating

	various options with relevant key stakeholders. Defines user requirements, creates user stories and personas.
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC)	By collect feedback and improvement suggestions for the different concept variations, POC verifies if a high-level concept is accepted by potential users and other relevant stakeholders. Initial feasibility study shows whether the concept can be developed. Evaluate technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept.
TRL 4: Prototyping in lab	Co-create quickly multiple design variations, features and functionalities by following rapid prototyping approach. Lab test prototype functionality, usability, and user acceptance in iterative co-creation-test cycle. Identify and address any immediate design flaws, usability problems or issues relating user acceptance before proceeding to next phase.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment	Transform user experience / working prototypes to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected in relevant environment and meets the predictions.
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment	Verify that high-fidelity prototype which closely resemble the final solution adequately addresses all critical features in relevant environment. Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.
TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment	Validate that near final solution (or final solution) is functioning at system level in operational environment. Start at scale and by using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment	Validate in operational environment. Focus on similar issues as in TRL 7 but in more large scale and longer duration.
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance	Monitoring the safety, quality and performance after solution has been released on the market. Focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions. Evaluate long term social and business impact. Help businesses make informed decisions that can lead to increased sales, growth and new opportunities.

Table 8 defines more detailed living lab TRL levels characteristics and includes following dimensions: research environment, solution name, functionality/interactivity, solution maturity, exploratory and confirmatory research aim. The criteria and descriptions are modified and reworded on the basis of priorly presented three TLR scales and definitions collected during the literature review.

Table 8 Detailed Living Lab TRL levels characteristics

Title	Research environment	Solution name	Functionality, Interactivity	Solution maturity	Exploratory research aim	Confirmatory research aim
TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation	Laboratory	Idea	None	A group of needs, problems, opportunities and/or ideas identified. Not been proven feasible.	Investigate a problem or topic to generate new ideas and hypotheses.	Prioritize needs and ideas.
TRL 2: Concept co-creation	Laboratory	Visual prototype	None, or very limited	High-level speculative and static concept transforming to concept prototype without or very limited functionality. Focuses on explaining and describing overall design concept and user interactions. Based on sketches, diagrams, drawings, compositions, mock-ups, wireframes, digital models, storyboards, paper interface and/or descriptive text. Non	Investigate a topic in more detailed to co-create and formulate concept and value hypotheses in iterative or parallel manner.	Prioritize options to determine the most appropriate way to proceed with further development.
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC)	Laboratory	Alpha prototype	Very limited		Explore different human, technical, economic, and environmental aspect to verify what is the best approach to develop the solution.	Test value hypothesis and confirm or reject them. Focus on user acceptance and feasibility.

				interactive to very limited interactivity.		
TRL 4: Prototyping in lab	Laboratory		Limited	User experience / working prototypes transforming from low to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. First working models to identify and	Co-create rapid functional prototype versions. Focus on the basic functionalities.	Verify usability, and technical feasibility to find out the most promising options having highest cost/profit ratio and user acceptance.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment	Relevant		Moderate	resolve usability, design and technical issues. Can have substantial flaws or missing functions.	Continue to iteratively refine the prototype based on the collected feedback and co-creation inputs.	Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected while meeting the predictions.
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment	Relevant	Beta prototype	High or near full	High-fidelity prototype with near fully functionality that closely resemble the final solution and adequately addresses all critical features. Technical feasibility fully demonstrated.		Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.

TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational		Near full or full	Production prototype near final solution (or final solution) functioning at system level		By using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment. Start in small scale and increase the scale gradually to full scale.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational	Pilot prototype	Full	Final complete solution at system level.	Refine and commit to final solution.	
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance	Operational	Final solution	Full	Final complete solution at system level ready for sale.	Refinement via versioning strategy.	

A research environment refers to the physical in which research activities take place. It encompasses a range of factors, including the facilities, equipment, and resources available to research. Living lab research can take place in one of the three research environments:

- **Laboratory Environment:** An environment that does not address in any manner the environment to be encountered by the solution or its subsystem, or component during its intended operation. It is a facility providing controlled conditions in which scientific or technological research, experiments, and measurement may be performed. In living lab context, laboratory can also refer to common “office” facilities such as meeting room or office desk. Covers TRL steps from 1 to 4.
- **Relevant Environment:** Relevant environment is the specific subset of the operational environment that is required to demonstrate critical "at risk" aspects of the final product performance in an operational environment. Relevant environments include e.g. virtual, modelling and simulation environments as well as field environments (i.e. real-world settings) where researchers can simulate physical or social phenomena in controlled way. It is an environment that focuses specifically on "stressing" the solution advance in question. Covers TRL steps from 5 to 6.

- **Operational Environment:** The environment in which the final solution will be operated. Covers TRL steps from 7 to 9.

3.5 Part 5. R&D Services

Figure 3 presents the logical relationships between different living lab R&D services and key living lab asset repositories.

Figure 3 Logical relationships between different living lab R&D services and key living lab asset repositories

There are following six touch points (left side of the figure) between living lab infrastructure provider and Living lab research infrastructure end user (a.k.a. customer).

- **Need for contacts** refers to situations where customer needs to get an access to right business contacts for marketing, sales or networking purposes.
- **Need for data** refers to customer need to have access to living lab's open data repository.
- **Need for equipment or facility** refers to a situation where customer wants to conduct the research itself but do not have adequate equipment or facility available.
- **Learning interest** refers to customer willingness to strengthening an organization, community, or individual's knowledge and skills regarding living labs.
- **Research / Innovation need or idea** refers to a gap or deficiency in knowledge or understanding that requires further investigation through research whereas innovation need refers to a gap or opportunity in a particular field, industry, or market that requires a new and creative solution or approach.
- **Funding need** refers to customer need to acquire funding for the research and innovation activities.

R&D services are classified in the following three phases, which each includes multiple R&D services.

- **Customer acquisition** (red colour) refers to the process of attracting and gaining new customers for a living lab. It includes identifying potential customers and reaching out to them through

various innovation ecosystem orchestration activities and converting them into paying customers.

- **Detailed project planning** (yellow colour) refers to creating a detailed plan for a living lab project by refining the objectives, scope, timeline, budget, resources, and tasks required to achieve the project goals as defined in funding proposal. The amount of work varies how much work has been done already during the offer preparation or in funding application process.
- **Project implementation and dissemination** (green colour) covers the execution of the all the task as defined in the project plan by following iterative living lab innovation process.

The key living lab assets repositories includes following repositories:

- **Stakeholder population repository** refers to all end-users (a.k.a. study participants), living lab research infrastructure end-users, Business-to-Business Customers (B2B) and research experts which a living lab has access and is able engage when needed.
- **Open data repository** refers to all open data set that a living lab has made available via virtual access user interface or similar access point.
- **Course and study material repository** refers to all kinds of study materials, lectures and courses which are available for capacity building purposes.
- **Methods and tools repository** consist of all methods and tools which a living lab has.
- **Devices and technologies repository** includes all technical devices which a living lab can use for collecting data or somehow use for facilitating research activities.
- **Validated questionnaires and instruments repository** refers to all scientific questionnaires, scales or similar which have been validated and found to work in living lab research context.
- **Publication repository** includes all scientific and professional publications which a living lab has made available via open access.

This Figure is not yet included in the Standard as it was not yet discussed and approved by the Harmonization Body and Board.

Two updates were introduced in Part 5, and these are the new Table 11 that included information about the new categorization of services in Back office, Supporting and R&D as well as the identified inputs and outputs. The Services were also presented based on their offered frequency, starting from the ones that are being offered by most LLs.

4 Standard Version 0.4

This Section will be the fourth (v0.4) public version of Living Labs Standard. This Standard is considered Version 0.4 as there are still sections that are not defined and have not undergone a full cycle of Harmonization. As v1.0 we are considering the first version that will contain information for all available sections and will be delivered by the end of the project, on M36. This Section is structured in such a way so that it can be separated from the rest of the deliverable and published in the VITALISE wiki page as a standalone document.

4.1 Introduction

The European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) – an international non-profit association promoting and enhancing user-driven innovation ecosystem defines living lab is *“a user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”* (<https://enoll.org/about-us/>).

This wiki serves as an open space for the public review of the harmonization version and encourages open discussion about the various items that are presented. The information presented in this wiki will be updated every six months and published after approval from the governance Board and Body of the Harmonization process. In each section you can find when and by which each version is approved (e.g., “Approved by the VITALISE H2020 Living Labs' consensus report on XX/XX/XXXX”.)

The VITALISE Harmonization process is governed by two main groups, the VITALISE Harmonization Body and the VITALISE Harmonization Board. By VITALISE Harmonization Body we refer to a wider community of stakeholders consisting of Living Lab researchers and practitioners, healthcare professionals, policy makers and professionals that are interested in research performed in Living Lab infrastructures. VITALISE Harmonization Board aims to co-ordinate the Harmonization procedures and practices and is consisted of representatives of each Living Lab in the consortium as well as independent representatives from the Health and Wellbeing domain as well as policy makers. Representatives of other Health and Wellbeing Living Labs are also encouraged to join. This board will take decisions regarding the Standard Versions.

The aim of this Living Lab standard is to guide Living Lab operators and researchers to execute, develop and maintain a harmonized framework for systematic Living Lab practices. It is not a rigid and strict representation of what Living Labs are doing but it rather be used as guidelines towards the identification of common approaches. Living Labs are structures that encourage serendipity in the way that they are working and should be handled as such. The standard versions concern mainly the LLs but they also borrow knowledge, expertise and experience from various other domains, like open science, citizen science, open innovation, innovation management, responsible research and innovation etc. on a sharing basis. Within this framework, there are several tools and methodologies exploited in LLs which could also be applied in several other research contexts.

By Establishing Living Lab management system, the Living Labs will:

1. Promote the expansion and growth of Living Lab movement beyond current actors and customers,
2. Stimulate cross-organization and transnational research collaboration,
3. Enable data sharing and comparison of the research results,
4. Increase research quality, and
5. Define a common terminology and language among researchers and practitioners.

The Figure 4 defines the conceptual overview of the living lab management system presented in this standard document.

Figure 4: The key elements and conceptual overview of the living lab management system

The following key elements will concern the Living Lab community and will be further assessed in the next Standard Version.

1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) – terms and definitions: LLL introduces, lists and shortly defines a comprehensive catalogue of terms associated and included in different parts of the living lab standard (i.e. 2 to 9). The LLL is grounded on Wikipedia type of user interface, where definitions including overlapping terminology, will enable quick jumping between different descriptions and to in-depth descriptions in other standard sections. LLL will help to discuss living lab related issues among the different stakeholder, who currently are using varying terminology.

2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM): “A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The purpose of the LLBM part is to identify different attributes associated with each nine BMC element. Having a unified way to describe LLBM enables quantitative business model comparison between different living labs as well as open ups possibilities to track changes in business model strategies.

3. Research process: The part ‘Living Lab research process’ focuses on defining the key steps to execute and define a living lab research methodology. The part is comprised of (1) a common template to define research protocol, (2) ethical and data management plans, (3) participant recruitment procedures, (4) infrastructure selection procedure, (5) data collection procedures, (6) data analysis and comparison practices and (7) fair data practices for opening data. Each phase consists of aim, outcome and maturity level description. Furthermore, research process phases are interlinked with other living lab standard parts in order to identify which other items are relevant for each research process phase. Having a standard way to describe living lab research design helps

developing a unified research methodology, which enables a robust results comparison across different studies, increasing the research quality.

4. Innovation process: Living Lab innovation process part focuses on defining in an unambiguous way, the different innovation management process phases which are or can be covered during the living lab data collection phase. This part defines an iterative and agile user-centered innovation and design process and align the phases with Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept. TRL is widely adopted concept to describe developed solution maturity level. Respectively to research process, different innovation process phases are interlinked with other Living Lab standard parts in order to identify which of the other items are relevant for each process phase.

5. R&D services: R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its' customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities or parts of the Living Lab standard, needed to accomplish living lab R&D project as whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. In the long run, the aim is to define the Minimum Acceptable Service Level for each service type in order ensure service quality across the different Living Labs.

6. Living lab Research Infrastructure (RI): This part provides a classification schema and definitions for different types of Living Lab infrastructures. In regulation No 1291/2013, European Union Parliament and Council of the European Union (2013) defines RIs as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields”. The definitions and descriptions for (1) single-sited, (2) distributed, (3) virtual and (4) mobile living lab facilities are provided.

7. Data collection approaches. Data collection approaches consist of the following three sub-parts: (1) methods and tools, (2) devices and technologies and (3) validated questionnaires and instruments. This part provides a collection of practical data collection approaches, which can be combined in multiple variations when defining a living lab project research methodology.

7A Methods and tools part identifies and describes the different types of specific research methods, tools, and practices, which can be used for data collection during a living lab project. Among these are e.g., interviews, workshops and surveys. In the future, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular method in different living research contexts.

7B Devices and technologies defines a commonly used technological solutions to collect and analyse living lab research data. Correspondingly to 7A methods and devices, the standard will be used for sharing the best practices and defining the appropriate ways to utilize the particular technology in a research setting.

7C. Validated questionnaires and instrument consists of a numerous scientifically validated surveys, scales, interventions or similar, known to be reliable measure-certain phenomenon. The Standard will especially promote questionnaires and instruments which are multilingual and freely available. If multiple instruments are available to measure same phenomenon, standard will make recommendation to make selections.

To conclude, it is important to clarify that the above-described conceptual overview and the included key elements of the living lab management system are preliminary concepts. Therefore, the names, details and concept itself can be changed in the following versions.

4.2 Scope of this document

This is the fourth draft version of the Health and Wellbeing Living Labs Standard (Version 0.4). The structure and content of this document will be continuously improved and a new version will be released every 6 months. The information presented is a result of an analysis performed in the VITALISE project and more details about the analysis can be found in the Deliverables of the project. The Parts that are not presented here are the ones that have not yet undergone a full circle of Harmonization. The rest of the document presents:

- **PART 1 Living Lab Lexicon (LLL):** Collection of terms that are widely used in Living Lab performed activities.
- **PART 2. Living lab business model:** The identified end users that can use the R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- **PART 3. Research process:** presenting the Living Lab research phases.
- **PART 4. Innovation process:** presenting the Living Lab Innovation phases.
- **PART 5. R&D Services:** A list of R&D services provided by Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.
- **PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure:** a first categorization of existing Living Lab infrastructures.
- **PART 7A. Methods and tools:** In this standard version identified methods and tools are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions.
- **PART 7B. Devices and technologies:** In this standard version identified devices and technologies are presented as a part of R&D service descriptions.

4.3 PART 1. Living Lab Lexicon (LLL)

It is clear that most stakeholders in Living Lab ecosystem do not always use the same 'language' and the words used may allude to different concepts. This can sometimes lead to confusion and misunderstandings and can become even more apparent when talking to different 'players' within the Living Lab communities. VITALISE is creating a Living Lab Lexicon (LLL) with the aim to create a repository where Living Lab key terms can be identified, defined, and shared with the Living Lab community and beyond. The overall vision is to facilitate and increase understanding and communication between the different 'players' within the Living Lab communities and all those who come in contact with Living Labs.

Moreover, some words/terms can have different meanings depending on the context of use (same term/word but more than one meaning). We also observe that some groups use different words to represent the same concept (different word/term but same or very similar meaning). To represent these main groups of potential users (Academia, Industry, Government, Citizens), we decided that it is important to include words/terms from the Innovation process and the Research process. In doing so, we will strive to ensure that the definitions included in the Living Lab Lexicon will reflect the diversity of context and use by the various potential users.

Below we present the first LL concept map that integrates various definitions and their interlinks.

Figure 5 Living Lab concept map

4.4 PART 2. Living Lab Business Model (LLBM)

“A business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value” (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). LLBM part is grounded on Business Model Canvas (BMC) approach (Ibid.), which consists of the following nine different elements. (1) key activities, (2) key resources, (3) partner network, (4) value proposition, (5) customer segments, (6) channels, (7) customer relationships, (8) cost structure and (9) revenue streams. The living lab standard defines common attributes associated with each nine BMC element.

This standard version focuses on defining customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs.

4.4.1 Customer segments in Health and Wellbeing Living Labs

End user: A person who ultimately uses or is intended to ultimately use the product, service or process. In living lab projects, the end user is defined as a primary study participant who voluntarily participates in research after giving informed consent to be the subject of the research.

Living lab research infrastructure end user: A person or organization who purchases or uses living lab research infrastructure services to conduct a specific contract-based research and development activity (often focusing on specifically defined end user group). Living lab research infrastructure end user can also be study participant (a.k.a. end user), if living project is focusing on developing living lab services and infrastructure.

End users can be classified as non-professional and professional groups. Typical non-professional and professional end-user groups in health and wellbeing includes the following:

- **Non-professional end users:**
 - **Consumers:** Those who buy goods or services for their own use.
 - **Public health and social service clients:** Those who use public services.
- **Professional end users**
 - **Health professionals and managers:** A person providing health care treatment and advice based on formal training and experience. Also known as healthcare professional or healthcare worker.

- **Social care workers and managers:** Those providing the practical support to help people cope with the day-to-day business of living based on formal training and experience.
- **Policy and decisions makers:** Those responsible for making policies and decisions at local, regional, national or international level.

Business-to-Business Customer (B2B): B2B-customer is an organization that purchases living lab services from a living lab. B2B-customers can be classified to private, public, education/ research, civil society organizations and networks/cluster groups as follows:

- **Private sector organizations:** (business developers and researchers)
 - Tangible equipment and device manufactures
 - Health and social service providers
 - e-health, IT system and digital technology providers
 - Wellbeing and wellness service providers
 - Pharmaceutical companies
- **Public sector organizations:**
 - **Local level:** Municipals, cities and other local level public organizations providing e.g., health and social services such as primary health care.
 - **Regional level:** e.g., Regional hospitals providing secondary and tertiary care, councils, parliaments, and governments as well as other administrative organizations operating at regional level.
 - **National level:** Government agencies, departments or temporary pointed working groups responsible for the specific functions such as health and social services.
 - **International level:** European commission departments and agencies as well as other organizations operating at international and transnational level.
 - **Public funder:** Government or other European, national, regional or local public institutions who is providing public funding for a specific living lab living lab research project via call for application process.
- **Education and research organizations:**
 - **Higher education institutes:** Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences
 - **Other educational institutes** covering early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary education
 - **Public research institutions/organizations** such as technical research centers and government laboratories.
 - **Private research organizations** such as technology and innovation centers
- **Civil society organizations:**
 - Non-governmental organizations (NGO) and nonprofit entities operating at international, national, regional or local level.
- **Networks and clusters:**
 - Company cluster organizations and company networks
 - International, national, regional and local networks

Typical approaches to define non-professional end users (a.k.a. study participants) in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 Classification approaches of non-professional end users commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Age groups			
Specific age range			
Adolescents	Adults	Older Adults	General Population

Adolescents Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy			

Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Schizophrenia	Multiple-Sclerosis	Parkinson Disease
Post-Stroke Patients with Moving or Linguistic Disability	Mild Cognitive Impairment	Sleep Disorders: e.g., Apnea, Hypopnea	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			

Older Adults Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Parkinson Disease	Mild Cognitive Impairment	With Disability
Healthy with Possible Chronic Conditions			

General Population Health status (disease, disorder or disability)			
Healthy	Ipf Patients	Prostate Cancer	Down Syndrome
Chronical Diseases: e.g., Persons With Chronic Pulmonary (Copd)	Cardiological Or Other Conditions (Aphasia)	Breast Cancer Survivors	

Typical approaches to define professional end users in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 10.

Table 10 Classification approaches of professional end users, students and organisations commonly acting as a primary study participant in a health and wellbeing living lab research project

Informal Caregivers			
Part of adults and citizens' group			

Health Care Professionals / Formal Caregivers			
Doctors	Social workers	Physiotherapists	Psychologists
Registered nurses	Practical nurses	Physicians	

Students			
Medical	Engineering	Computer Science	Pedagogues
English Literature	Nursing	Physiotherapy	Social Services.
Health Care Management			

Organizations			
Hospitals	Nursing homes	Care homes	Home care Organizations

Network organizations	Day care centers		
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Living lab research infrastructure end users and B2B-customers in health and wellbeing living lab projects are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Researchers' expertise

Researchers' expertise	Brief use case description
Citizen scientists, users as co-researchers	User empowerment, training, design, analysis and implementation of strategies and methodologies for user engagement and for raising awareness and generating citizen participation.
Computer, technology scientists	Developing systems/tools/ technologies, testing and evaluating an ICT tool, prototype and real-life testing, computer vision & AI, Virtual Reality & Augmented Reality, Cybersecurity.
Data scientists	Collecting, analysing and interpreting digital data, such as data analytics in healthcare and digital patient recordings (how patient information recording process is managed and utilized during the intervention by using digital tools in simulated situations).
Rehabilitation (physical, cognitive) experts	Physiology, physiotherapy, occupational health research, rehabilitation and prevention. Cognitive diseases assistive technology, neuromuscular rehabilitation assistive technology.
UX research and assessment experts	Developing the process for user experience design (UXD, UED, or XD) supporting user behaviour through usability, usefulness, and desirability provided in the interaction with a product or service, addressing all aspects as perceived by users with a focus on the quality of the user experience. Studying and experimenting the best practices for UI/UX and evaluating user's experience in different situations and while using different tools.
Clinical expertise researchers	(Doctors, nurses, healthcare workers, specialists, physiotherapists etc.), conducting research of healthcare services and practices, research on symptomatology or epidemiology of a disease, analysis of clinical effects of research performed in the study, e.g., via real life testing.
Policymakers	Studying the impact of new service models or new collaboration models in healthcare, designing or improving policies, gathering requirements for improving health and wellbeing of citizens, co-creation of research methodologies for policy making.

Biomedical researchers	Studying biochemical and physiological functions, investigating how the human body works with the aim of finding new ways to improve health. Biomedical engineering knowledge (Home hospitalization, Transitional Care, Multifunctional interaction), as well as digital biomarkers analysis (e.g., for cognitive state).
Business developers	Studying the product-market fit, matching a solution with a societal need, learning about the user acceptance of products and services, as well as about potential products to develop, willingness to pay, business model and ideal route to market.
Innovation and design management researchers	Ecosystem and innovation management research, social network analysis. Evaluating how health and wellbeing ecosystem operates between different actors at local, regional, national and international level, including also scaling and commercialization.
Accessibility design experts	Validating accessible architectonics and escape route models with VR experiment and real-life simulations.
Ergonomics and safety experts	Implementation and validation of ergonomic technologies/services to support workers and system performance, promoting ergonomics in working environments, improving both health/well-being and productivity, while avoiding occupational hazards.
Organizational studies experts	Co-creation, experimentation, organizational research, experts by experience / peer support included. Evaluation how multistakeholder collaboration and co-creation is done and how effective it is. Evaluates experimentations and experimentation culture. How users are involved into these processes.
Neuroscientists	Focusing on the brain and its impact on behaviour and cognitive functions (cognitive neuroscience, EEG-based BMI research, protocol / paradigm testing, study framework evaluation).
Psychologists (clinical, social, developmental, neuro)	Studying the behaviour and the mental wellbeing of participants, conducting psychometrics evaluation and real-life setting experimentation/observation/real life testing.
Social workers/researchers	Conducting an investigation in accordance with the scientific methods and tools, studying the impact of new care models and/or care innovations on society, developing models for a caring and inclusive society.
Sport science experts	Experimenting novel training methods, and their effectiveness in various dimensions such as safety, engagement, and physical capabilities. Studying the

	impact of physical movements in various functions and wellbeing features.
Communication studies experts	Defining written, oral, visual and digital communication within a certain workplace. Evaluating (multi professional) healthcare team collaboration, communication and debriefing in various healthcare situations in simulated environments (especially in Simulation lab).
Performing arts experts	Creative health improvement (e.g., for cognitive decline) through music and dance (example: redesigning public spaces into healthy spaces: test and validate Smart methodologies, products and services through folk dance).
Pedagogues/educators	Evaluating different pedagogical approaches and their impact learning performance (especially in Simulation lab).
Applied economics experts	Evaluating cost and performance in different healthcare processes, situations and public health.

4.5 Research process

The table below presents the Living Lab research process phases and details about the services that Living Labs can offer in each phase. These phases are inspired by research in the Health and Wellbeing domain but can be extended to other domains as well.

Table 12 Living Lab Research phases

Phases	Research process steps	Related living lab services
Planning phase	1. Identifying the research problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use living lab capacity building services to gain knowledge and skills to conduct your own living lab study. Conduct small pre-study with a living lab. Use e.g., co-creation sessions or expert opinion services to gain better understanding of the research topic or to formulate robust research design. Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping with living lab to determine suitable sample. Use open data repository and omit data collection entirely or partially.
	2. Conduct literature review and collect other relevant background information	
	3. Formulate research questions and/or hypothesis	
	4. Define the research design and determine sample	
Preparation phase	Acquire funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply temporary living lab research funding if it is available e.g., via open call. Utilize living lab grant writing and funding application support services or join to consortium who is applying funding. Use living lab networking services to gain access with funders.

	Research infrastructure selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Get in contact with a living lab and familiarize yourself with their research infrastructure key assets and service offerings. Living lab research infrastructure covers single-sited, distributed, virtual access and mobility facilities, which each have different strengths. Clarify your research needs in intake and matching process with potential living lab infrastructure providers. Wait for their offer. Send equipment and/or facility rental request to a living lab.
	Ethic approval	Living lab will prepare and manage ethical application process for your study.
	Participant recruitment	Living lab will use their stakeholder population repository to recruit study participants for the study.
Implementation phase	5. Data collection	Living lab will conduct data collection according to research protocol and will manage the project for you. You will benefit from wide range available methods, tools, devices, technologies, validated questionnaires and instruments, which can be tailored to your research needs.
	6. Analyze data	Living lab will conduct data analysis if agreed in project contract. Translations or summary reports from local language to English are made if there isn't common language between customer and collected data.
	7. Interpret results	Discuss and interpret result in a co-creative manner with diverse group of experts from living lab innovation ecosystem.
	8. Write research report	Co-author scientific and professional publications with living lab researchers.
Dissemination and valorisation	9. Disseminate findings	Utilize living lab sales, marketing and networking services to disseminate and valorise your research results to various stakeholder groups. Gain visibility by sharing your publication in living lab publication repository.

4.6 PART 4. Innovation process

This Table presents the Living Lab innovation process phases with detailed information about the activities performed at each stage. The Living Lab Innovation process stems from the TRL levels of innovation process.

Table 13 Living Lab innovation process phases

Title	Research environment	Solution name	Functionality, Interactivity	Solution maturity	Exploratory research aim	Confirmatory research aim
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TRL 1: Need assessment and ideation	Laboratory	Idea	None	A group of needs, problems, opportunities and/or ideas identified. Not been proven feasible.	Investigate a problem or topic to generate new ideas and hypotheses .	Prioritize needs and ideas.
TRL 2: Concept co-creation	Laboratory	Visual prototype	None, or very limited	High-level speculative and static concept transforming to concept prototype without or very limited functionality . Focuses on explaining and describing overall design concept and user interactions . Based on sketches, diagrams, drawings, compositions, mock-ups, wireframes, digital models, storyboards , paper interface and/or descriptive text. Non interactive to very limited interactivity.	Investigate a topic in more detailed to co-create and formulate concept and value hypotheses in iterative or parallel manner.	Prioritize options to determine the most appropriate way to proceed with further development.
TRL 3: Proof-of-concept (POC)	Laboratory	Alpha prototype	Very limited		Explore different human, technical, economic, and environmental aspect to verify what is the best approach to develop the solution.	Test value hypothesis and confirm or reject them. Focus on user acceptance and feasibility.

TRL 4: Prototyping in lab	Laboratory		Limited	User experience / working prototypes transforming from low to moderate depth and breadth of functionality. First working models to identify and	Co-create rapid functional prototype versions. Focus on the basic functionalities.	Verify usability, and technical feasibility to find out the most promising options having highest cost/profit ratio and user acceptance.
TRL 5: Prototyping in relevant environment	Relevant		Moderate	resolve usability, design and technical issues. Can have substantial flaws or missing functions.	Continue to iteratively refine the prototype based on the collected feedback and co-creation inputs.	Validate that prototype as a whole and at component / subsystem level is working and performs as expected while meeting the predictions.
TRL 6: Demonstration in relevant environment	Relevant	Beta prototype	High or near full	High-fidelity prototype with near fully functionality that closely resemble the final solution and adequately addresses all critical features. Technical feasibility fully demonstrated.		Validate that prototype as a whole can operate reliable and consistently over time and is ready for operational usage.
TRL 7: Small scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational		Near full or full	Production prototype near final solution (or final solution) functioning		By using rigorous evidence-based data validate social/human, economic

				at system level		viability, scalability, positive/negative effects, as well as any unintended consequences or indirect impacts that may arise in operational environment. Start in small scale and increase the scale gradually to full scale.
TRL 8: Full scale demonstration in operational environment	Operational	Pilot prototype	Full	Final complete solution at system level.	Refine and commit to final solution.	
TRL 9: Post market testing / surveillance	Operational	Final solution	Full	Final complete solution at system level ready for sale.	Refinement via versioning strategy.	Monitor and evaluate safety, effectiveness, performance and quality over longer period of time.

4.7 PART 5. R&D Services

R&D services refer to a group of common R&D services, which a Living Lab can offer to its customers during the different Living Lab R&D process phases. Each service combines one or more data collection approaches or other activities. R&D Services are parts of the Living Lab standard needed to accomplish a Living Lab R&D project as a whole or part of it. Each service description defines the type of service and additional details related to service delivery such as technical and functional quality. Living lab R&D services are classified into the following categories:

1. Testing and validation
2. Community and network building
3. Project planning and management
4. Co-creation
5. Capacity building
6. Advisory services
7. Market and sales support
8. Infrastructure and data management

It is noted that some of the services can be included in multiple categories.

Table 14 Services categorization, inputs and outputs

Input	PoV	Service	Output	Category
Application	client	Temporary research funding	funding decision	supporting

Course enrolment	client	Capacity building	skills and capabilities increased/knowledge about LLS	supporting
Request/application	client	Equipment and facility rental	tender and usage of equipment	R&D
Research idea/contact from the network	client	Grant writing	grant application	supporting
Call search	LL	Call identification	targeted calls	back office
Request/application	client	Public procurement applicant support	help meet the tendering criteria/process	supporting
Request/application	client	Public authority procurement support	defining market dialogue/innovative procurement	supporting
Application with information about goal/data	client	Access to data	data	R&D
Idea/offer request with info about topic	client	Intake and matching	understanding client's request/requirement	supporting
New and existing contacts	LL	Innovation network orchestration	partner and collaboration network	back office
Network and contacts	LL	Panel management	repository of stakeholders	back office
Project plan/research protocol	LL/client	Participant recruitment	study participants	
Project plan/research protocol	client	Stakeholders and partner analysis and mapping	identification of relevant stakeholders and/or study participants	supporting/R&D
Project plan/research protocol	client	Expert opinions and	expert opinion	supporting/R&D

		advisory services		
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Co-creation session	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Usability testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Concept and proof-of- concept	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Clinical trials	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Idea selection and testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Large-scale real-life testing and piloting	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Prototyping test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Simulation test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Small-scale real-life testing and piloting	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Competitor and market analysis benchmarking	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Impact assessment and validation test	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D

Idea/offer request with info about topic	client	Marketing and sales support	sales lead	supporting
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing	outcomes/report of the session/data	R&D
Research plan/ input from previous R&D activities	client	Legal, regulation and safety standard support	outcomes/report of the session/data	supporting/R&D

Depending on the nature and the scope of each service, the structure and the elements of the descriptive information vary. Below, follows a brief explanation of the R&D services structure:

Table 15: R&D services structure

Section	Description
Description	In the description field a general overview of the service is given (e.g., definition, scope, followed processes etc.)
R&D service categories	Here it is indicated the category (or categories) to which belongs the service
Key characteristics in living lab context	In this field are highlighted the most important points/aspects of the service in a Living Lab framework
Pre-tasks	By pre-tasks we mean the several steps that are considered important to be completed before the delivery of the service
Participants' role	Participants' role refers to the particular actions/activities that are expected to be achieved by the stakeholders during the service delivery
Objectives	In this part are identified the various goals that are envisaged to be accomplished during the delivery of the service
Methods	This field refers to the methodology that stakeholders could follow for the service implementation (e.g., focus groups, training sessions, workshops, seminars, presentations, interviews etc.)
Tools	By tools we mean the specific instruments which could be possibly exploited during the service (e.g., questionnaires, sensors, Teams meeting, Zoom, whiteboards etc.)
Process phase	Here it is indicated the phase or stage during which the service is usually delivered

4.7.1 Expert opinion, and advisory services

Description: Expert(s) who have long-standing practical and/or scientific experience in the field of enquiry provide(s) a well-founded written or oral answer for your questions, including the ethics domain/ethics guidelines, and offer(s) advisory services on the use of specific equipment. Expert(s) are discussing ideas and problems from a different angle to respectfully challenge, test and refine ideas (e.g., as devil's advocate looking for problems). Qualified and traceable arguments in favor of and against a specific position in an applied issue to support decision-making and development activities. Professional work is a paid service, but "consultation" can be a free of charge service. In most cases it is done by Living Lab on its own, hosting organization personnel, subcontractor.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management, Capacity building, Advisory services, Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Typically consists of one-to-one relationship between the customer and the expert, but may include opinions from multiple experts.
- Internal or external experts (local, national and international experts)
- Multidisciplinary collaboration/Pool of experts

Objectives:

- Offer advice on UX or usability studies,
- Consulting care solutions (ICT and devices), in specific/narrow fields in which Living Lab has experts (e.g., energy consumption calculations),
- Consulting on consent and ethics requirement and processes,
- Consulting technical solutions (ICT, medical and other devices, sensors, wearables, health apps, machine learning, medical engineering)
- Consulting legal issues, networking and contacting people (e.g., doctors, academia, pharmacy, healthcare professionals, policy makers, local ecosystem actors), research ideas,
- Innovation management, interventions,
- Creation of training materials and processes

Methods: One to one and group discussion, advisory board, expert identification

Tools/Online tools: ethical tools, training materials

4.7.2 Idea selection and testing

Description: Idea testing is a low-cost and quick process in which high-level ideas are selected (i.e. ranked) or tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews, surveys or during the workshop. In order to conduct idea testing, different high-level ideas are pre-described in written or in visual format, and then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback on the already existing idea proposal. Feedback can also include improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Objectives:

- Collect feedback, prioritize ideas or different alternative options,
- Lowering development risk by selecting the best/most promising idea for further development,
- Challenge the ideas from different perspectives

Methods: Co-creation workshop, interviews, focus groups, surveys, questionnaires, small group discussions, informal talks

4.7.3 Co-creation session

Description: Co-creation session is a facilitated group activity to find solutions for a specific problem by gathering ideas, solutions and insights from workshop participants while using variety of methods. Depending on the workshop focus, it may comprise ideation, concept development and testing. Typical duration for short workshop is from 45 minutes to 90 minutes, medium-length workshop from 90 minutes to 3 hours, and long-workshop from 3 hours to 1 day. The number of participants may vary depending on how many facilitators are available, and what kind of working methods are utilized. Typically, a workshop facilitated by a single facilitator consists of six to eight persons. Number of participants are sometimes numbered to enable them to work in pairs.

R&D service category-ies: Co-creation, Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Fundamental features: Requires (1) facilitator(s), (2) interaction/is interactive, (3) iterative process
- Can be applied in almost all phases: e.g., ideation, concept creation/testing, prototyping, prototype testing
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- It is a service but also a generic method
- Duration varies, but usually 2-3 hours
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: researchers, clinicians, students (e.g., paediatric project, project on language and communication). Depending on the concept all actors of the quadruple helix are contacted, number of users depends also on the stakeholders. Engagement of different stakeholders can also be achieved by running series of sessions

Participants' role:

- In the beginning of the innovation process, involve the users as the creators
- If there is a product with higher Technology Readiness Level (TRL), a ready Minimum Viable Product (MVP) is more like a focus group,
- Need finding session, focus group is more of an evaluation,

Pre-tasks: prepare session upfront with the sketches, if focus group - open questions (sent beforehand), workshop preparation template

Objectives (varies depending on researchers' interest):

- Co-creation session: Finding solutions for a specific problem with or without prototypes or mock-ups. Co-creating the actual design, sketch interfaces, make the solution tangible, Drafting (prototypes, drawing), mock-ups
- Demo-session: specifically, setup to explain about the use of a prototype or market ready product and gather (first) feedback. Often done before launching a test.
- Business model session (broader, a service?): developing and defining a business model (e.g., potential customers, sales channels, distributors, value chain, the Willingness to Pay, revenue streams etc.

Methods: Brainstorming, use simulations, group discussion / focus groups, semi-structured focus group, survey, questionnaire

Tools: Projection walls, visual mock-ups, use tangible tools for prototyping (e.g. wearables), team groups, polling (tech); questionnaires, focus groups, idea generation techniques, post-it notes, creative supplies, art supplies,

Online tools: Online system for idea generation, Teams meeting, Zoom with breakout rooms, Google meet, Miro whiteboard, Mural.co

4.7.4 Impact assessment and validation test

Description: Impact assessment is a formal, evidence-based procedure that assesses the total outcome that comes as a result of the tested activity, above and beyond what would have happened anyway. Depending on the duration and scope of the validation process impact can be evaluated on individuals, organizations and the society in the short, medium and long term. Validation is the documented act of demonstration that a product or a service will consistently lead to the expected results. Validation test ensures that the product or the service actually meets the defined requirements and demonstrates that the solution fulfils its intended use when deployed on appropriate real environment.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The validation test is usually designed by LL
- Validation testing has to meet some minimum TRL level in order reliable test the solution impact

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will consistently lead to the expected results and meet defined requirement
- Evaluate social impact
- Quantify change after solution usage

Methods: Survey, observation, pre and post measurement (short and long term), quantitative measures (e.g., physiological measures), feasibility study, usability study, interviews

Tools/online tools: Questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors, thermal cameras

4.7.5 Concept and proof-of-concept tests – concept feasibility study

Description: Concept test is a low cost and quick process in which a high-level concept is tested with real end-users via different methods such as interviews and surveys. In order to conduct a concept test, preliminary concept description must exist in written or visual format, which is then communicated to the real end-users or experts. The main aim is to collect feedback for the initial concept proposal and its possible variations. Concept test can also include a feasibility study, which also covers technical, economic, legal, operational and scheduling issues relating the proposed concept. In all, concept-testing phase verifies if a concept has market interest, while feasibility study shows if the product or service based on concept can be developed. Collected feedback also includes improvement suggestions.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Core service in LL

Participants' role: Two main actors (projects and companies), joint work among Living Labs and interested partners/stakeholders

Process phase: After concept co-creation

Objectives:

- Verify if a concept has market or research interest,
- Testing early “prototypes” to get feedback for development, identify improvement suggestions,

- Concept feasibility test focuses on verifying if concept can be technically/economically done (preliminary assessment),
- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs, identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests, personalized in the client need and varies case by case

Methods: Survey, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz

Tools: Paper prototype, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), visual VR can be used to test-multitasking (real work), long term evaluations, interviews, questionnaires

4.7.6 Innovation network orchestration

Description: Establishing productive working relationship between existing and previously unconnected but complementary actor parties and helping them (companies, public health and other sector, academia, and end-user stakeholders) to work together properly and well. Handling conflicts and supporting interactions.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Capacity building

Objectives:

- Establish new collaboration relationships,
- Promote Living Lab methodology and raising awareness,
- Lobbying Living Lab movement

Methods: Events, seminars, webinars, conferences, one-to-one meetings, site visits, publications (scientific and professional), memberships in local/regional/national/international associations/networks

4.7.7 Large-scale real-life testing and piloting

Description: Similar to small-scale testing but with a longer duration or larger number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group. During piloting, the aim is to evaluate the full scale and near or fully functional product(s) or service(s) at the system level in real environment with real end-users to make sure that the solution is scalable. Includes often impact assessment and validation testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually, the aim of the testing defines the number of participants
- Sometimes, for large numbers the LL can hire a specialized company for support

Objectives:

- Evaluate scalability,
- Evaluate system level impact and functionality,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, longitudinal study, sensors, interview, survey, observation, ethnographic studies, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

4.7.8 Prototyping test

Description: Prototyping test is a low cost and quick process in which a product or service with limited functionality and interaction is tested with real end-users. An interactive prototype product or service must be available so real end-users or experts can experience it. This prototype test can be, for instance, an interactive mock-up of a web service, which interface looks like a real thing. One can navigate through different screens and see simulated content. Also, the service prototype can

consist of role-playing exercise to simulate service encounters. The main aim is to collect feedback on a 'close to real' user experience as possible, but at a lower cost. Different methods such as interviews, surveys and observations can be used.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- From rapid prototyping to the MVP
- IT solutions/Physical and cognitive exercises

Objectives:

- Similar to proof-of-concept but testing higher fidelity solution,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,
- Provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Survey, observation, demo-session, interview, Wizard of Oz, usability tests, role playing

Tools: Paper prototype, wireframes, interactive mockups, scaled down prototypes, visual dummies close to final (visual UI), video recording, usability questionnaires, eye tracking

4.7.9 Small-scale real-life testing and experimentation

Description: A small-scale real-life experiment is a small-scale and short-term preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility of the suggested product or service and to improve it based on the testing result. Testing includes a small number of test participants who are representing the real end-users of the target group.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Usually lab-based studies
- Can mostly involve qualitative feedback
- Testing quality and user satisfaction,

Objectives:

- Verify that the developed solution will work also in real-life setting,
- Evaluate usability before engaging more people in testing,

Methods: Testing in real-life setting with real users, survey, interview, survey, observation, diaries, qualitative/quantitative methods, pre and post measurement

Tools: Validated questionnaires, sensors

4.7.10 Stakeholder (and partner) analysis and mapping

Description: Identifying groups, organizations, and people who are relevant stakeholders. Prioritizing and ranking stakeholders based on their perspectives and interest. Mapping the relationship between different stakeholders and company objectives. Deliverable(s) Written report.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Co-creation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Within a research context / for programs and projects.
- Trying to promote a diversity-centered design

Pre-tasks: Searching and listing all the interested stakeholders/partners, contacting them, and then mapping possible contributors

Objectives:

- Identifying relevant/key/negative stakeholders,
- Identify stakeholders' interest,
- Provide information to participant recruitment

Methods: Focus group, workshop, interviews, questionnaires methodology, social network analysis, two-dimensional matrix (e.g., power, influence, interest/need, support/attitude), primary/secondary/tertiary stakeholder, the salience model

Tools: Online whiteboard (e.g., Miro), stakeholder mapping template

4.7.11 Usability testing

Description: Usability testing is a technique used to evaluate a product by testing it in order to give direct input on how real users use or would use the product or service. Usability inspection is conducted when a professional evaluator inspects a user interface and gives an expert opinion regarding the usability. This approach does not involve real user. Usability testing with real users includes real users who have no prior exposure to the product or service. In the context of Living Labs is mostly provided real user testing.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Objectives: Identify usability problems, provides development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,

Methods: Moderated/unmoderated, remote/in-person, comparative testing, open ended explorative testing, user satisfaction, phone/video interview, usability lab testing, session recordings, observation

Tools: SUS, QUEST, feasibility assessment and other several tests, eye-tracking camera

4.7.12 Capacity building

Description: Training, knowledge sharing and awareness raising, site visits and event arrangement. Offering training for end-users and/or practitioners to improve their skills and knowledge about Living Lab approach, co-creation, iterative development and healthcare and wellbeing market. Stimulating knowledge sharing and awareness raising by publishing professional and scientific publications and arranging events, site visits and seminars.

R&D service category-ies: Capacity building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- The way of knowledge sharing and transfer depends on the project and on the purpose
- Use of short-term or long-term methods and courses
- Material can be both created for a purpose but also some available online

Participants' role:

- Service beneficiaries become trainees
- Living Labs can offer support for the design and facilitation of capacity building programs

Methods: Co-creation methodology, focus groups, training sessions (tech & non-tech), ethical training & legal in large scale settings, seminars, presentations, workshops, webinars, forums, websites and web-engines, events, site visits, publications, summer schools, degree program, methodological training, how to use new product

4.7.13 Living Lab project planning and management

Description: Planning project goals, costs, schedule, list of deliverables, delivery dates and resources. Written project plan for one or multiple innovation stages is made. In the project management, planned tasks are completed by executing, monitoring, controlling, and closing the work of a project team to achieve specific goals and to meet specific success criteria at the specified time.

R&D service category-ies: Project planning and management

Objectives:

- Successful development and implementation of all project procedures,
- Supervision and quality control,
- Internal/external communication,
- Optimization of the allocated resources,
- Getting clients and funding,

Tools/Online tools: Project and planning management tools, Microsoft Teams, Microsoft Excel, email, phone, messaging application

4.7.14 Competitor and market analysis and benchmarking

Description: Quantitative and qualitative methods are used to evaluate the size of the market both, in volume and in value (also known as market studies). Customer segments, buying patterns, competition, and the economic environment are defined to identify the regulations and the barriers to entry. Defining the market by listing and describing current, future, direct and indirect competitors and analysing their competitive offering (e.g., SWOT) and user experience. Comparing offerings by measuring the performance of the developed products, services, or processes against those, which are considered to be the best in the industry. Can consist also of literature reviews to a search and evaluation of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services, Market and sales support

Participants' role: Competitors or stakeholders interested in collaborations, can be done by students or experts.

Objectives:

- Identify the “space” for innovation, not analysing only specific segments, but also looking for new opportunities
- Analyse market acceptance, support scalability and transferability potential, focus can be domestic/international/global market,
- Identify direct and/or indirect competitors, qualitative or quantitative description of the market, focus can also be in research context or innovation management practices

Methods: Desk research, acquiring the information from the experts in the field, following the market as a job profile/duty, the people working know specific segments/areas, bibliometric studies, literature reviews to a search and evaluate of the available scientific or professional body of knowledge for the given subject or chosen topic area, technology exploitation, market analysis, benchmarking, other methods combined with interview(s) with a leading reference organisation or expert(s), assessment of technologies, knowledge syntheses (systematic and scoping reviews), evaluations methods of intervention (ETMI method), workshops and sessions, measures of satisfaction of users

Tools: SWOT analysis, business model canvas, Innovation management standard (CEN/TS 16555 - covered 7 standards, after ISO 56002:2019)

4.7.15 Intake and matching

Description: During this service, the customer's (e.g., a company, SME, a start-up, a researcher) development and testing needs are clarified for the project planning purposes. It also includes the process of mapping the customer's needs and co-designing of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project and Living Lab capabilities to offer the particular project.

R&D service category-ies: Community & Network building, Co-creation, Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Can be both open discussion or more focused
- Usually at the beginning of the research process
- Can be virtual/online or in person event
- Duration varies-30 minutes (very short form) to few hours or days. In most of the cases there are multiple meetings taking place/more than one contact
- Often multi-stakeholder approach: Researchers, clinicians, customers, students

Participants' role:

- Customers as co-creators

Pre-tasks:

- Discuss and understand who the customers are and what their needs are.
- Agree to a plan -usually it is made a document/contract- (set goals, explore the different services, engage the operational team
- Revise & follow-up activities with the customer

Objectives

- Make a project proposal/offer between the relevant stakeholders
- Make a project contract

Methods:

Client's needs elicitation methodology, interview/focus group/questionnaires for defining the project and collecting the needs, co-design of the strategic planning in relation to the target/purpose of the project

4.7.16 Simulation test

Description: Simulation is a technique that creates a situation and environment, which allows end-users to experience a representation of a real event in a risk-free environment. A predefined simulation scenario defines a particular set of conditions to resemble authentic situations in a location where a simulation experience takes place to test and to gain understanding of tested solution and related human interactions. After simulation event, facilitators and end-users re-examine the simulation experience, and various aspects of the completed simulation are discussed.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context

- Mainly for ICT solutions
- Simulation labs, smart home that simulate real-life home/specific scenarios to simulate real space

Objectives:

- Simulate real-life situations and behavior but lower cost,
- Identify improvement suggestions and usability test,

- Provide development recommendations based on user/patient/customer experience and needs,
- Identify key measures to investigate in follow-up tests

Methods: Simulation test, virtual reality (VR), usage scenarios, interview, debriefing, observation, survey, Wizard of Oz, sensors, usage logs, hospital ward, interactive patient mannequin, usage scenarios,

Tools: Audio recording, video recording

4.7.17 Clinical trials

Description: Clinical trials are experiments or observations done to evaluate the effectiveness and safety of new solution by monitoring its effects on large groups of people. Subjects are typically divided into two or more groups, one having “real treatment” by using the developed solution and the other group(s) using tried-and-true solution or not using any solution. The results are compared between the groups to evaluate the impacts.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and validation

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Clinical trials are similar to impact assessment and validation test activities but follow more strict validation and approval process.

Participants’ role:

- Customers as co-creators

Objectives

- To find out if new solutions are safe and effective
- Get official approval for new solution

Methods:

- Has multiple phases and classes which depend on the developed solution

4.7.18 Grant writing and funding application support service

Description: Offering tailored support by identifying the proper local, regional, national and international funding instruments, helping to write and manage a funding application process including finding the right partners for the project if needed. In most cases a Living Lab will become a project partner, but it can also be provided as a paid service without participation.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Acquiring/providing funding for “customer” to execute a Living lab project or buy Living Lab services,
- Getting project partner for a Living Lab project

4.7.19 Panel management

Description: Panel is a pre-existing group of pre-screened people (e.g. patients, practitioners etc.) who have given their consent to take part in different research activities over an agreed period. Panel members have given their contact details and other profiling information, which enables fast recruitment for specific research activities as they come up.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building, Project planning and management, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Group of patients, students but also experts, experts by experience and other staff can be used as a panel (agreement is necessary in every case)
- Having engagement procedures in place (win to win situation), social activities

Objectives:

- Enable fast participant recruitment,
- Lower the management effort (no need to fill profile information multiple times)

Method: survey, recruitment collaboration with medical professionals (e.g., in hospital ward)

Tools/Online tools: intake questionnaire, phone, open calls in social media/web, posters, email, personal invitations

4.7.20 Post-market surveillance and market acceptance testing

Description: Post-market surveillance is a “real world” test of medical innovations in patient subgroups. It is a practice of monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market. Market acceptance testing focuses on collecting market feedback for the next revision development and tracking the solution performance in real competitive market conditions.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually within a clinical or community research context (within the context of specific projects/the products that come out as research outcomes) and not as a standalone service.
- As normal customer feedback collection and health promotion, for continuum improvement of the tool

Objectives:

- Monitoring the safety of a medical innovation after it has been released on the market,
- Evaluate social impact,
- Identify new opportunities for business and research

Methods: Survey, observation, interviews, helpdesk logs, technical logs, complain reports, pre and post measurement (long term), market studies

Tools/online tools: questionnaires, validated scientific scale/questionnaires, sensors

4.7.21 Temporary research funding

Description: Providing funding (or an investment) for research, product and business development for small and medium-sized companies or start-ups. Typically, funding is targeted for short-term small-scale experiments or if an externally funded project has resources for this kind of activity (e.g., open calls). Also, it can be done in collaboration with local research centers, publicly funded “development companies” and networks or similar.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Objectives:

- Providing funding to execute small scale Living Lab project (e.g. testing)

Methods: Offering funds within funded projects for small-scale testing or co-creation

4.7.22 Access to data

Description: Referring to service, which enables customers to access or retrieve data from one or more databases consisting of relevant data, based on mutual agreements respecting ethics and GDPR, which can be used for development or testing purposes.

R&D service categories: Testing and validation, Market and sales support, Infrastructure and data management

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Usually 2 sources: already existing data, new data collected
- Data must be anonymized and encrypted
- Consent from participants have been previously acquired by the LLs when it's required by ethical and legal legislations
- Type of data: demographics/personal data, health-clinical data (e.g., cognitive, treatment changes, physical performance, care to rehabilitation), measure data, sensors' data (brain activity)
- For open data, FAIR data principles should be followed
- Ethical approval and GDPR processes when needed

Pre-tasks:

- Create a database to store data
- Define the accessibility of the database (public or limited access) and how data are collected (in an integrated way or occasional/ad hoc databases/infrastructures)
- It is, usually, needed a request that is passed to the responsible of databases

4.7.23 Marketing and sales support

Description: Providing marketing and sales support for 1) making right contacts by giving business contacts, sales and business leads, 2) setting up and arranging meetings and events, 3) showcasing products and services in a showroom or giving online/onsite visibility in Living Lab own communication channels, 4) providing “user approved” certification, and 5) offering soft landing support to help to set up business in given Living Lab country or region.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- It can be introductory to healthcare companies and service providers and goes up to the point of developing a BM

Objectives:

- Finding right contacts and customers for Living Lab clients,

Tools: “user approved” certification, showroom, showcasing, business meetings, interviews, events, soft landing services, sales/business leads

4.7.24 Public procurement support services

Description: Public procurement (e.g., related to research activities) is governed by EU and national rules. Support with public contract issues and the public procurement process is given to help clients to meet the tendering criteria and/or join the tendering process. Also helping public authorities to establish market dialogue when developing the public procurement announcement. This includes Pre-Commercial Procurement and innovative procurement processes.

R&D service category-ies: Community and network building

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Pre-commercial procurement, innovative procurement, public procurement
- Project based
- Validation Software (integration) - Hardware (operational validation in real environment)
- Legal design and decision-making support

Methods: Planning process based on co-creation, pre-commercial procurement (PCP), innovative procurement

4.7.25 Equipment and facility rental service

Description: Offering equipment, labs, spaces, human resources and other facilities for rent. Some Living Labs do this based on a win-to-win agreement where money does not change hand. Also, some Living Labs require research collaboration when renting.

R&D service category-ies: Testing and Validation, Co-creation, Advisory services, Infrastructure and data management

Participants' role: In some cases, researchers can visit the LL and use the provided facilities free of charge

Objectives:

- Getting temporary human, space, technical or other facility resources,
- Enable research collaboration

Methods: Payment, research collaboration grounded on Living Lab resources

Tools: Simulation lab

4.7.26 Foresighting (trends, weak signals and wild cards)

Description: Foresighting is a practice of exploring expected and alternative futures. Trend is a general tendency or direction evident from past events increasing or decreasing in strength of frequency of observation. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue that may become significant in the future. "Wild card" is a high-impact event that seem too incredible or is considered too unlikely to happen; yet many do happen.

R&D service category-ies: Market and sales support

Objectives:

- Policy consulting,
- Create a future vision,
- Identify new opportunities and risks,

Methods: Back casting, brainstorming, user/citizen panels, workshop/session, expert panel, interview, literature review, role playing, scenarios, survey, SWOT, wild card & weak signals, science fiction/crazy ideas

4.7.27 Legal, regulation and safety standard support

Description: Providing support to navigate to the legal, regulatory and safety standard requirements and help planning to meet the requirements.

R&D service category-ies: Advisory services

Key characteristics in Living Lab context:

- Legal design and decision-making support
- Support on signed agreements, protocol
- In some cases, external contractors for IPR, RGDP

Objectives:

- Similar to expert opinion and advisory services but focusing on legal and regulatory issues

4.8 PART 6. Living lab research infrastructure

In regulation 1291/2013, the EU Parliament and Council of the EU define Research Infrastructure (RI) as “facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields” [1]. Living lab RIs consist

- **Single-sited facility:** Unified single body of equipment at one physical location
 - Laboratory or smart home
- **Distributed facility:** Facilities, resources and services that are geographically scattered in multiple location
 - City, city district, outdoor space (e.g. nature/hiking trails)
 - sensor networks, network of homes
- **Virtual access-based facility:** Resources and services that are exclusively available via online internet-based tools.
 - Access and ability storage scientific data and repositories, tools for virtual collaboration, various computer services,
- **Mobile facility:** Facilities and resources which can be easily moved to from one place to another
 - Handheld devices and non-handheld equipment

4.9 PART 7A. Methods and tools

This section includes two templates that can be used as a tool for the designing and reporting of co-creation sessions within the LLs. In particular, the first template consists of several parts that are crucial for thoroughly describing the design and the implementation of a co-creation session and the second one includes the information considered important for reporting it.

4.9.1 Template for designing a co-creation session

CO-CREATION SESSION

JRA (Joint research activity) x

Small-case study name:

Co-creation session with: (e.g., care professionals, patients, informal carers)

General recommendations:

*The objectives and scenarios can be split up: e.g.: 1 session for care professionals & 1 session for patients/informal carers etc. We would advise you to organize separate sessions for professionals and patients/informal carers and also, to adjust and fill the template separately for each group. The set-up is quite similar, but the focus is sometimes different. It is suggested a min of 4 participants and a max of 12. If wanted, you can video tape, as a back-up (*attention to the ethics considerations – videotaping should be included into the consent form).*

Other recommendations:

- Delay erodes quality
- Debriefing and reflection with the team (moderator and observer) improves quality
- Keep the research questions in mind
- Stick as close to the data as possible (quotes, words used by participants)

RESEARCH QUESTIONS & AIM

Describe the research questions and the objectives of the co-creation session, depending on your target group and the information you want to collect.

*Some general research questions can be the same across the different regions, to be able to compare and report some results later on.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals	Session with participants (e.g., older adults)
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	What experiences do the participants have from previous... (possible benefits, difficulties)?
To what extent is technology accepted by the clinicians? (attitude towards technology)	To what extent is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

*Please structure and enumerate your research questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”).

STAKEHOLDERS

Define all the stakeholders of your co-creation session

- The number of facilitators
- The number of observers/documenters
- The number of participants

STRUCTURE & PLANNED ACTIVITIES

Define the structure of your co-creation session(s), the activities you are planning to include (e.g., open discussions based on pre-defined questions, brainstorming, demonstration of a selected tool)

GUIDING QUESTIONS

Define the questions you are planning to ask to the participants.

*Please structure and enumerate your questions in order to be easier to report the answers afterwards (Report template: section “Output summary & main findings”)

*Some overall questions can be the same for a general part across the small-scale studies within the JRAs.

e.g.:

Session with health care professionals

Research question	Guiding questions
What is their current experience with (intervention) technology?	From your previous experience, are there any technological means that are exploited during...? Do you personally use any kind of technology for supporting...?/How do you use technology?
To what extent is technology accepted (attitude towards technology)?	Are you open to use technology? Are your patients open to use technology?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during...?	Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...? Is there anything that you would like to be different or that could be improved?
How do they follow up on their patients?	

Session with participants (e.g., older adults)

Research question	Guiding questions
What experiences do the participants have from the use of technology so far (possible benefits, difficulties)?	Do you use any kind of technology in...?/ What are your experiences from previous (challenges, benefits)...? What kind of support you think is needed for you to use technology in...?
To what extent is the use of technology accepted by the participants for supporting... (benefits, challenges)?	Are you open and willing to use technology?/ How possible do you think it is for you to use technological means when you...?
What are the advantages and limitations of using technology during ...?	What would be the biggest return for you to use technology during...? Are there any difficulties or challenges that you think it's possible to encounter when using technological means during...?

TOOLS & MATERIAL/RESOURCES

Describe all the tools and materials you are planning to use during your co-creation session(s) (E.g., informed consent to sign for each participant, templates, post-it, pen/pencils, blackboard etc.)

EXPECTED OUTPUTS

Define the expected outcomes of your co-creation session(s) (e.g., current status, needs, challenges, expectations/what is needed to happen in the future)

EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE

Here we will define the common participation questionnaires (one for the participants and one for the LL facilitators) that will be used across the study after the end of the co-creation session.

You will find a proposed questionnaire in the last pages of the report template

PLANNED DATE-TIME, SETTING & AGENDA

Define the date, time, place/setting, as well as the activities and their duration within the co-creation session. Indicate also, who will be engaged in each particular slot of the co-creation session.

Define the room set-up (e.g., board room style/round table etc.)

e.g.:

Date: Monday 30 May 2022

Time: 12:00-13:30

Place:

Time	Duration	Activity	Team
12:00	10'	Welcome and registration	all
12:10	10'	Presentation	all
12:20	5'	Split participants into tables	table
12:25	5'	Provide the templates and material	table
12:30	40'	Activities/questions - open discussion	table
13:10	15'	Each team presents briefly what was discussed	all
13:25	5'	Questionnaire	all

4.9.2 Template for reporting a co-creation session

REPORT_CO-CREATION SESSION

LL name	
WP & Small-case study name	
Facilitator(s)	
Observer(s)/documenter(s)	
Date of co-creation session	
Number of participants (total)	

Facilitator team

List the name and the email of the facilitator(s) and the observers(s)/documenter(s) involved in the session. Indicate their role in the session and their profile (e.g. psychologist, nurse, occupational therapist, physiotherapist, gerontologist etc.)

Participants' profile

Fill in each participant's profile in a different row, checking the appropriate cell.

Serial number	GENDER			Age	PROFILE (define the stakeholders you will engage)		
	Male	Female	Neutral/ Other	Year of birth	Stakeholder 1	Stakeholder 2	Stakeholder 3
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
6							
7							
8							
9							
10							
11							
12							

Serial number	Education level								
	ISCED 0: Early childhood education	ISCED 1: Primary education	ISCED 2: Lower secondary education	ISCED 3: Upper secondary education	ISCED 4: Post-secondary non-tertiary education	ISCED 5: Short-cycle tertiary education	ISCED 6: Bachelor's or equivalent level	ISCED 7: Master's or equivalent level	ISCED 8: Doctoral or equivalent level
1									

2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									

Serial number	Technology literacy				Previous contact with VITALISE project	
	Basic	Intermediate	Advanced	Excellent	YES	NO
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
7						
8						
9						
10						
11						
12						

ONLY FOR THE HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS

Serial number	How many years have you been in practice?	What area of speciality do you currently work in (i.e. neurology, musculoskeletal etc.)

1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		

Session goals

Briefly describe the objectives of the co-creation session.

List of questions & activities

List and briefly describe the questions / activities that guided the discussion for collecting value insights from the participants

List of tools and materials used

List and briefly describe the list of tools and materials used during the co-creation session.

Output summary & main findings

Give the output summary of the session, including, if possible, 4 main topics: current status, needs, challenges, expectations. You can also include the exceptions, the remarkable examples, and experiences, /how the participants felt. If possible, you can also register relevant quotes/insights from participants.

Topic XX: Main findings:
Topic XX: Main findings:

Incidents

Mention and briefly describe here any possible incidence that occurred during the co-creation session that wasn't planned to happen or hasn't been foreseen. If possible, mention also how you handled it / how you adjusted to this unexpected condition.

--

Photos

In this section add some photos of the event (5-6). It is nice to have some photos depicting the whole event, e.g., with the tables, hands, materials etc., including also the participants, IF THEY HAVE CONSENTED, (probably blurred *ethics considerations). Also, please try to include some photos that have the VITALISE logo in the background (e.g. from a presentation, a banner).

Questionnaire output

In this Section report the output of the VITALISE participation questionnaire (ANNEX 1). This questionnaire is filled by the participants of the co-creation session. Each participant could write his/her name if he/she wants and the facilitator must report the profile category (older adult, caregiver, clinician) for whom they have provided their names an N/A for those have not.

Profile	1	2	3	4	5
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			
	Choose an item.	Choose an item.			

Happiness of the team

This questionnaire is filled by the Living Lab (facilitators) team. The goal is to record possible problems in the procedure, the communication and the assigned work. Each Living Lab should fill only one questionnaire that depicts the average impression of the whole team.

1. Assign a score from 1-5 in each co-creation session:

Co-creation session	
How do you feel about the amount of work assigned to you in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the amount of work you did in this co-creation session?	
How do you feel about the quality/value of work you did in this co-creation session?	

2. What would you change? (Free text response)

3. What did you like more? (Free text response)

ANNEX 1

1. How do you feel about this co-creation session?

2. Would you like to be with us in possible next sessions? YES NO

3. What did you like most on this co-creation session?

.....

.....

.....

.....

4. What you did not like on this co-creation session?

.....

.....

.....

.....

5. Is there anything you want to propose as a possible improvement?

.....

.....

.....

.....

4.10 PART 7B. Devices and technologies

This Part presents a taxonomy for identifying and classifying the data that are collected in Living Lab environments and consequently link the devices that are used for collecting each data category. The aim of the taxonomy is to help finding the appropriate digital data collection tools for living lab research and/or expand understanding about available tools and their possibilities. Furthermore, the taxonomy aims to facilitate data collection by driving a unified representation schema of the collected datasets enabling the the cross-organizational collaboration and the accessibility of Living Labs to external stakeholders.

Table 16: Devices and technologies provided by Living Labs

			Definition
Categories of devices for data monitoring and collection	Environmental monitoring		characterize and monitor the environment, establish environmental parameters and conditions. As environment we refer to the person's surroundings either indoors or outdoors
	Human monitoring	Biometrics	biological measurements — or physical characteristics — that can be used to identify individuals and their unique characteristics such as fingerprint scanning or voice recognition
		Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	electrical biosignals, or bioelectrical time signals, usually refers to the change in electric current produced by the sum of an electrical potential difference across a specialized

			tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system
		(Primary) Vital signs	a group of the six most important medical signs that indicate the status of the body's vital function according to HL7 standard
		Body size and composition	measurement of a person's body, used as qualifying elements for vital signs
		Cognitive ability and mental processes	Measuring the processes involved in the acquisition of knowledge, reasoning and management of information and the brain-based skills we need to carry out any task
		Activity and behavioral monitoring	monitoring the individuals' physical activities and tracking their performance. Monitoring behavior and activities of daily living (ADLs)
Categories of technologies for interventions	Assistive Technology		technologies used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals, the feeling of autonomy, safety and general wellbeing or also supporting participation.
	Extended reality - XR (VR & AR)		allows for a two-way flow of information through an interface between the user and the technology through a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world
	Serious Games		all the digital games that are used as interventions for health and wellbeing not including XR

Table 17: Devices and technologies subcategories

Category	Subcategory
Environment monitoring	Concentration levels (air pollution levels, humidity, atmospheric pressure, air quality)
	Technical alerts (e.g. flood, smoke)
	Environmental Temperature (air or water temperature)
	Luminosity
	Audiovisual devices
Biometrics	Face recognition
	Voice recognition
Electrical Biosignals and physiological monitoring measures	EEG (electroencephalography)
	ECG (electrocardiography)
	EMG (electromyography)
	Vo2 (maximal oxygen consumption)
	Blood oxygen
	Blood sugar level
	GSR (galvanic skin response)
(Primary) Vital signs	Diastolic blood pressure
	Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate
	Body temperature
	Respiratory rate
	Oxygen saturation
Body size and composition	body height - lying (measure on a horizontal surface)
	body weight
	body measures (fat, mass, muscle, water and bone)
	circumference measures (head, neck, biceps, waist, hip, chest, forearm, thigh and calf)
	Body Mass Index
Cognitive ability and mental processes	cognitive tasks and paradigms
	memory
	processing speed
	attention
Activity and behavioral monitoring and tracking	walking speed
	orientation

	human body location (indoors or outdoors)
	movement monitoring
	human balance
	physical activity level
	physical performance
	sleep
	steps
	stress level
	physical performance
	technology usage habits and patterns
	fall detection
	gesture recognition and detection
Assistive Technology	reminders & alert
	coaching
	training
	walk assistance
	support activities of daily living (ADLs)
	natural language understanding
Extended reality – XR (VR & AR)	Virtual reality (VR)
	Augmented reality (AR)
Serious Games	cognitive gaming
	physical gaming - exergames
	educational games

5 Conclusion

This document presents information about the collection of data and analysis towards the creation of the Standard Version 0.4 for Living Labs in the Health and Wellbeing domain. Although the name of this deliverable is Standard version 4, the authors decided to name the Standard v0.4 as not all the parts have undergone Harmonization process yet. From the work that has been done so far, the authors concluded that there are various domains that will benefit from the Harmonization processes and that there is need for Harmonization in various contexts (Section 4.1). Standard Version 0.4 is an improved and updated version of 0.3. There is still some missing information for specific sections which will be included during the upcoming standard versions, after conducting some envisaged activities for updating the corresponding parts. The focus of this standard version was mainly the addition of the Innovation and Research Phases and the work done to update the R&D services. An important amount of data was also collected for the publication of VITALISE Open Calls. The analysis of these data resulted in several updates to the standard presented in Section 3. The process will continue in an iterative way and its results will be released every 6 months. The VITALISE consortium envisions to create a methodology that will continue to evolve even after the end of the project and that will be adopted by other thematic areas Living Labs (e.g., urban Living Labs) to capture the particularities of each domain and to identify the similarities across Living Lab practices.

6 References

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